

Cassava bags: Understanding consumers' awareness towards bioplastics in buying decisions through eco-friendly attributes

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Abstract

Annually, an average restaurant generates 100,000 pounds of plastic waste. That is the reason it is important to make a significant difference to our environment by providing customers with accurate product information or raising their knowledge of biodegradable plastics. Cassava bags are a great alternative to the plastic and paper bags that are commonly used in restaurants for take-out orders. However, the more people we question about their knowledge of cassava bags, the more we discover that they are completely unaware that such good products exist at all. To encourage people to save the environment, it is also important to provide them with information on perfect alternatives that they can use in their everyday lives. Introducing them to those who have the power to make a difference is essential in encouraging people towards environmental preservation. This can be accomplished by beginning with consumers and restaurant employees. In this study, data were obtained by using an online survey and in-depth interview. Thus, the quantitative method and qualitative method were applied in this study. The targeted respondents for this survey were food and beverage consumers, aged 18-50 years old while in the in-depth interview, employees who have been working in the hospitality industry for three to five years were selected to participate in this study. Through their experience, they were able to share their insights and opinions about biodegradable take-away packaging and how it might affect the consumers buying decision in the long run.

Keywords: *Cassava; Biodegradable; Restaurants; Bags; Water-soluble.*

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Introduction

Plastic utilization has been happening through the years, and the effects of it on the environment can be seen and experienced by everyone. Plastic waste has affected the environment in negative ways considering the increasing waste since it does not decompose easily. People end up suffering by using it. Single-use plastic bags contribute an exceptionally enormous amount to increasing plastic waste since they have only one purpose and cannot be used again. To reduce plastic waste, the use of paper bags has been implemented by some local governments. The fact that paper bags are eco-friendly, biodegradable, and compostable still causes adverse effects in our environment. It causes deforestation as millions of trees are needed to be cut; pollution in the air by releasing nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide, and carbon dioxide; manufacturing a paper is equivalent to using more energy that produces more greenhouse gases and acid rains that worsen global warming (Crisostomo, 2012). It has been used in malls, groceries, bakeries, restaurants, and other types of businesses. It comes with varied sizes for distinct types of products that can be put inside. It is biodegradable, reusable, and recyclable. Since it does not have that much effect on the environment, like plastic waste, the local government units started implementing it to maintain the cleanliness of their covered areas.

Many people adjusted when it was implemented since it is not that easy to carry, unlike the plastic bag that does not require any support on the bottom part when you are carrying it. It is not easy to use when you are carrying foods that are cold or frozen since it melts, and you will need another plastic or eco-bag to replace it. On the other hand, bio-plastic bags are available, but not many people are aware of them. Cassava bags are like regular plastic bags but have a difference in decomposition. It is made with cassava starch, vegetable oil, and organic resins. The materials that are used in making this bag are biodegradable and compostable. The easiest way for it to decompose is to dissolve it in hot water, and it will not leave any waste that can be visible to the environment.

Food packaging has been a part of the food and beverage industry from the start, and it plays a huge role in the success of each establishment. For the restaurateurs, proper packaging symbolizes a good start of interaction with the customers because this is how they see how you want them to perceive your business establishment. Choosing a decision on what food packaging you are going to use helps with how you want the food to stay warm and safe, especially in this time of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Many restaurants closed their dining rooms to the public to prevent the spread of the virus, converting their service into takeout and deliveries. Consideration of food packaging is a huge part of this new normal because you still want the consumers or customers to feel that the service is still enough even though you are not executing it within their vicinity. Choosing the accurate packaging for your business should have benefits once you use it, and that is why it is significant to make smart decisions about it. In the food and beverage industry, cross-contamination should be always avoided because it is the transferring of bacteria from one place to another and it can occur in any phase of food production. Making sure that the products that you use for takeaway packaging are safe and durable helps the customer to trust the establishment, as well as the extra thought that was put into food packaging shows that the business cares about the well-being of consumers. Maintaining the temperature is also an important part of takeaway packaging because there is nothing worse than ordering food with excitement and consuming it cold. Lastly, food packaging also establishes identity for the customers. Using a specific theme that is related to your business can attract customers because it can differ from the normal ones that are already used by other establishments. There are many materials that are used in food packaging, such as plastic, paper, cardboard, Styrofoam, and the new trend, which is sustainable packaging or bioplastics.

For example, you are using sustainable packaging, and it is one of the values in your restaurant. It is a simple way to indicate that you are dedicated to serving people but also mindful of the effects of what you are using on the environment. Takeaway food packaging is not just a simple part of your business; instead, it is an opportunity to show the consumers what your business values since it is the first thing that the customers notice once they receive their orders.

Regular plastic bags have been used before by several establishments, including the food and beverage industry. It has been an innovation because it can carry different things and is considered a high-quality product. Plastic packaging has been present from the start, and it is what most industries in food and beverage use because of its durability and safety purposes. It preserves the freshness of the food and prevents the cross-contamination that is present in every phase of food production. Each customer in the food and beverage industry has used regular plastic bags, and the effect of it on the environment caused a major concern.

As we all know, plastic does not decompose easily and can be found everywhere in the world. This is one of the signs of its durability and is considered a harmful effect mostly on aquatic places since it prolongs the breaking down of plastics. There are also animals who are living there that suffer when they encounter plastic bags because there are limited plastic removal options since there is no one to help them with. Problems like this create struggles for the wildlife since they can eat those and cause them to die. Even though there are options for people to recycle regular plastic bags, it is still not enough because of new plastic waste every day, causing it to be a major problem everywhere in the world. As the use of plastic bags became a concern for the environment, reducing the use of them served as a solution for this rising problem. Internal factors can be controlled, thus the behavior and opinion about plastic bags by different

people. To control the use of plastic bags, paper bags were given an opportunity to be a substitute for regular plastic bags.

Related Literature

According to Bucatariu et al. (2017), environment adds value to the entrepreneurial environment. This value addition is based on consumer trends and preferences, but also on gaining a maximum profit. In general, the business environment must rely on turnover volume for the constant reinventing of products and services, of quality and prices. The planet is currently facing an increasing number of environmental challenges, which include climate change, global warming, droughts, water scarcity, floods, and pollution (Ahmed et al., 2018). People have experienced a lot of these environmental challenges that lead to people being open and aware of environmental issues not only in the country but all over the world. With these, many are now opting for sustainable living and are choosing eco-friendly products. People have this “green paper bag” image that we must get rid of. According to Jauhar et al. (2015), there are a lot of reasons paper bags are not actually eco-friendly. The production of paper bags itself already endangers the environment with cutting down 14 million trees every year, requiring more water in manufacturing it, which creates 70% more water pollution than the production of plastic bags, which intensifies global warming. Both paper bags and plastic bags endanger marine life as well as human life and can be harmful to the environment; they are not better than the other.

A conceptual model was created by Hoyer et al. (2017) to identify the clues and decision-making process involved in purchasing products and services that are already available on the market at a given moment. This model integrates four areas regarding consumer behavior, namely: (1) the psychological part; (2) the decisional process; (3) consumer culture; and (4) problems and results. This model is based on our understanding of how to conduct research on consumer behavior and consumption, facilitating marketing structures to formulate effective strategies and approaches to meet the demands of potential clients. But if we want to understand the consumers’ behavior in the business economy, according to Adlerian theory, we will have to consider the theories of the experts in emotional marketing that follow three stages, which are: the stage of awareness, the stage of consideration, and the stage of decision. To know the market opportunity of cassava bags in food and beverage establishments, we must make people aware of this product, its features, its benefits, its characteristics, and its attributes to proceed to the next stage, which is consideration and lastly decision-making.

Global demand from consumers for products and services has grown dramatically over the past decade, which is severely harming the environment and depleting natural resources. Global warming, rising environmental pollution, and a reduction in flora and fauna are a few of the major effects of harmful emissions (Chen & Chai, 2010). The concept of “sustainable development,” which highlights the importance of promoting sustainability and supports that kind of development that avoids detrimental effects on the environment and society, emerged because of this realization and concern for the environment and society. The goal of eco-innovation is to apply environmentally sustainable approaches to the production of goods and services at every stage (Veleva & Ellenbecker, 2001, as cited by Joshi & Rahman, 2015). Meanwhile, green consumption is typically associated with ecologically conscious consumption, in which customers consider the effects of buying, consuming, and discarding different products or making use of different green services on the environment (Moisander, 2007).

Grunert and Juhl (1995) stated that environmentally responsible purchasing is vital, as unplanned purchasing of goods can severely damage the environment. Specifically, consumer household purchases were responsible for 40% of the environmental damage. Consumers possess the capability to prevent or decrease environmental damage by purchasing green products. People must consider eco-friendly product attributes when purchasing a product, as it is very important.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to promote cassava bags in understanding consumers' awareness towards bioplastics in buying decisions through eco-friendly attributes used in selected restaurants in Bacoor, Cavite, to help reduce and prevent paper waste consumption as a market opportunity. Intending to develop alternate packaging products as an alternative to plastic packaging, which gives hazardous effects to the environment, a study is necessary to penetrate deeper into the consumers' actual needs and their favored features. From the research, it is expected that alternate packaging products could be developed in line with customers' awareness and motivate them to switch to this product. Empirical questions are formulated to answer the main objective which will guide this thesis:

1. To what extent is the consumer interested in the eco-friendliness of take-away packaging?
2. What are the key attributes that influence the buying and decision-making behavior of the consumer in purchasing eco-friendly take-away packaging products?
3. How will it benefit the selected restaurants in Bacoor, Cavite?

Methodology

Research Design

There are two sources of data: primary data and secondary data. The primary data are originated by the researcher for a specific objective of approaching the current issue. This data sourcing is designed for decision-makers in organizations that pay for well-focused and exclusive support. However, this data is costlier and more time-consuming in analyzing the data compared to secondary data. Secondary data are data that are readily available and collected for objects other than the problem at hand. The secondary data are more straightforward compared to primary data (Malhotra et al., 2020). In this research, primary data were obtained by using an online survey and an in-depth interview. Thus, the quantitative method and qualitative method are applied in this study. Primary data can be classified into two categories: quantitative and qualitative research. Qualitative research is usually unstructured research, which mainly focuses on the exploratory design on a small sample with the purpose of generating depth, insight, and understanding. Quantitative research strives to quantify data with some application of measurement and statistical analysis. There are certain cases where quantitative measurement can answer a specific hypothesis or research question (Malhotra et al., 2020).

Sampling Procedures

In this study, the researchers used non-probability convenience sampling with 100 respondents as the sample size. Researchers distributed online research questionnaires through Google Forms to the food and beverage consumers who participated during the data gathering procedure. The characteristics of the consumer were determined through the demographic questions that are included in the research questionnaire.

Research Questionnaire

The questionnaire was divided into three parts. The first part is an agreement statement through a Likert scale to measure how interested consumers are in purchasing eco-friendly packaging products. The Likert scale used a 5-point scale and started with 1 as strongly disagreeing up to 5 as strongly agreeing. The second part contains statements and questions about consumers' awareness of biodegradable plastic, and the last part is to determine the factors affecting the consumers' green purchase intention. The other questionnaire is for the structured interview for the food and beverage establishments' employees, where it

includes the name of the employee, how many years they are working in the hospitality industry, position in their work, residence, and their level of education. It is also divided into three parts, which are about their general knowledge about environmental issues, environmentally friendly products, and their interest in buying eco-friendly products. The table of interpretation that researchers used is as follows (Table 1):

Table 1. Interpretation of the research results

Scale	Indicator	Range	Verbal Interpretation
Agreement	5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree
	4	3.41-4.20	Agree
	3	2.61-3.40	Neither
	2	1.81-2.60	Disagree
	1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree
Awareness	5	4.21-5.00	Fully Aware
	4	3.41-4.20	Aware
	3	2.61-3.40	Neither
	2	1.81-2.60	Not Aware
	1	1.00-1.80	Not Fully Aware
Intensity	3	2.35-3.00	High
	2	1.68-2.34	Medium
	1	1.00-1.67	Low

Data Collection

Desk research and exploratory research were conducted to obtain preliminary information regarding attributes and their levels. The data collection process was done by distributing the online questionnaire to respondents. The online questionnaire used Google Forms as the platform to collect the data, as mentioned above. The targeted respondents for this survey were food and beverage consumers, aged 18–50 years old. To achieve the objective of the research, which is to elicit the awareness of food and beverage establishment consumers of eco-friendly packaging, respondents are provided with several choice sets made by researchers, and respondents need to choose one set of choices in each question. Demographic questions were also included in the questionnaire to be able to determine the characteristics of the consumer. The sample size for the survey was 100 people.

Data Analysis Procedure

The researchers made a request letter describing the purpose of the study and the respondents’ rights for the approval to conduct our study and for the distribution of research questionnaires in selected restaurants located in Bacoor, Cavite. After acquiring all the formal permission, the researchers screened possible respondents according to the respondent’s profile to determine the eligibility and credibility to answer. The data gathering procedure happened after the respondents agreed to participate. After collecting the data, the researchers analyzed all the respondents’ answers. The result determined and understood the consumers’ awareness towards bioplastics and how their buying decision was affected by the eco-friendly attributes.

Results

Table 2. Environmental awareness

Environmental Awareness	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
1. It is important to me that the products I use do not harm the environment.	4.54	Strongly Agree
2. I would describe myself as environmentally responsible.	4.20	Agree
3. I often buy eco-friendly products.	3.85	Agree
4. I am willing to spend a higher amount of money to purchase packaging products that are more environmentally friendly.	3.98	Agree
5. I am willing to make extra effort to purchase packaging products that are more environmentally friendly.	4.20	Agree

According to the data that can be seen above, the respondents strongly agreed that it is important to them that the products they use do not harm the environment (Mean = 4.54). The respondents also agreed that they describe themselves as environmentally responsible (Mean = 4.20); that they often buy eco-friendly products (Mean = 3.85); that they are willing to spend a higher amount of money to purchase packaging products that are more environmentally friendly (Mean = 3.98), and that they are willing to make extra effort to purchase packaging products that are more environmentally friendly.

Table 3. Biodegradable plastic awareness

Biodegradable Plastic Awareness	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
1. I am aware about bioplastic and its eco-friendly attributes.	4.05	Aware
2. I am aware that I can purchase bioplastic here in the Philippines.	3.63	Aware
3. I am aware that cassava bags are an example of a biodegradable plastic.	3.18	Neither
4. I am aware that a bioplastic like cassava bag can dissolve in hot water and be compostable.	2.78	Neither
5. Due to the bioplastics' characteristics and availability, are you aware that it might cost more than the regular plastic and paper bags?	4.16	Aware
6. Are you aware that the food and beverage industry can use bioplastic bags as take-away packaging rather than using plastic and paper bags?	3.85	Aware

The table shows that the participants are aware about bioplastic and its eco-friendly attributes (Mean = 4.05); that they can purchase bioplastic here in the Philippines (Mean = 3.63); that it might cost more than the regular plastic and paper bags due to the bioplastics' characteristics and availability (Mean = 4.16); and that it might cost more than the regular plastic and paper bags due to the bioplastics' characteristics and availability. However, it shows that the participants are being neutral or states that they have neither a positive nor a negative response about cassava bags as an example of a biodegradable plastic (Mean = 3.18) and that a bioplastic like cassava bag can dissolve in hot water and be compostable (Mean = 2.78).

Biodegradability, quality, and toxic-free ranked top in the list of factors that customers are considering while purchasing a product (Mean = 2.86). Since they are looking for environmentally friendly products, it should be toxic-free and biodegradable. Customers want to make sure that the products they are purchasing are of a good quality to use for a longer period. Since these three characteristics are ranked highest, consumers are aware of the importance of biodegradable products, implying that they are also contemplating the environmental effects of the products they use. Other factors that affect green purchase intention are the following: Durability (Mean = 2.74), Material Composition (Mean = 2.72), Availability

(Mean = 2.39), Convenience (Mean = 2.39), Price (Mean = 2.31), Design (Mean = 2.02), and Popularity (Mean = 1.85).

Table 4. Factors that affect green purchase intention

Factors	Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
A. Biodegradability	2.86	High
B. Quality	2.86	High
C. Toxic-Free	2.86	High
D. Durability	2.74	High
E. Material Composition	2.72	High
F. Availability	2.39	High
G. Convenience	2.39	High
H. Price	2.31	Medium
I. Design	2.02	Medium
J. Popularity	1.85	Medium

Discussion

Plastic utilization has been happening over the years, and the negative effects of it can be seen and experienced by everyone. To lessen the use of it, local government units have implemented the use of paper bags. The main ingredient in making paper bags are trees, and it causes deforestation as millions of trees are needed to be cut; pollution in the air by releasing nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide, and carbon dioxide; manufacturing a paper is equivalent to using more energy that produces more greenhouse gases and acid rains that worsen global warming (Ashrafi et al., 2015).

In lieu of the fact that plastic and paper leave visible waste, biodegradable plastics can be one of the solutions to lessen it. Biodegradable plastics look like regular plastic but have a difference in decomposition. A cassava bag is an example of a biodegradable plastic and introducing it to the food and beverage industry is a great way to present it to the public since it is not widely known as an alternative takeaway packaging. In the current era of capitalism and globalization, the primary goal of every producer is to increase his or her profit as much as possible. This is why the so-called “green image” appears on paper bags and plastic bags, which makes promises about being biodegradable and eco-friendly while in fact depleting our natural resources even further than they already are.

Consequently, to avoid being taken advantage of, a customer must be informed of his or her options. In this case, consumer awareness refers to the process of raising awareness about items that are ideal for the consumer’s environmental values. Consumers’ awareness of environmentally friendly products that are accessible but have not yet been purchased can potentially influence their intention to purchase environmentally friendly products. Price and the effort required to purchase these things are insignificant if the products are environmentally friendly, biodegradable, toxic-free, and of high quality. Furthermore, this survey shows that while most of the participants are environmentally conscious, they are only provided with minimal selections of eco-friendly items to choose from.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The researchers conclude that after hearing words like reusable, biodegradable, and recyclable, customers grew interested in the environmental friendliness of take-away packaging. Their understanding of environmental concerns has assisted them in selecting or becoming interested in environmentally friendly items. Consumers with a wide variety of preferences for eco-friendly qualities in eco-friendly goods used for take-away packaging in food and beverage businesses were drawn to the factors “quality,”

“biodegradability,” and “toxic-free” that influence and affect their buying decision in eco-friendly products. Most consumers are not fully aware that products such as cassava bags exist.

Given that cassava bags are significantly less expensive than the paper bags that restaurant establishments typically purchase, using these will be beneficial for both the food and beverage industries because it allows them to save money while also improving their environmental footprint. Based on the study and analysis of the answers on the questionnaires and interviews done by the researchers and physically finding some problems, this paper makes the following recommendation to the future researchers, local government units, residents, and employees of F&B establishments in Bacoor, Cavite:

1. The researchers suggest that questions for food and beverage personnel be improved and that they should be centered on how they plan to employ eco-friendly packaging items such as biodegradable plastics in their facility rather than their personal preferences.
2. The researchers suggest that consumers can be encouraged to use eco-friendly products if it is introduced to them (with a proper proposal and clear objectives) properly. That is why using the promotional plan can be one of the ways to start bringing awareness about the usage of cassava bags.
3. The researchers suggest that environmentally friendly businesses that sell biodegradable packaging can be supported by the local government unit of Bacoor by sympathizing with their vision since businesses like this promote sustainable packaging solutions that can be used as direct alternatives to plastics. If the local government unit supports the usage of cassava bags with implementation, then the production of the cassava bags may increase as well as the availability to the consumers.
4. The researchers suggest that with sufficient advertising and cooperation from the local government unit, food and beverage outlets may provide discounts to consumers who bring their own sustainable packaging, such as cassava bags, for their takeouts. This can be beneficial to both businesses and customers, as this is also one way to save money. They can start a new movement like “the ABCD’s in Bioplastics,” which stands for: use as an Alternative; Bring your own bioplastics; Cut; and Dissolve.
5. The researchers suggest planning and implementing events that encourage residents of Bacoor, Cavite, to join and be creative with their bioplastic. It is to increase the popularity of bioplastic, which can also increase the price factor of the purchase intention of the consumers.

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